

One Nation One Subscription: A Short-Term Solution, But the Diamond Open Access Path Shines Brighter

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India's [One Nation One Subscription](#) (ONOS) initiative, set to be operational from January 1, 2025, marks a significant step toward addressing the persistent challenge of unequal access to academic journals for researchers, educators, and students nationwide. By consolidating 13,000 e-journal subscriptions from 30 publishers into a single, unified package, ONOS promises to bridge the access gap, particularly for underfunded institutions. However, while ONOS addresses immediate disparities in access, it is inherently a short-term solution that does not address the underlying structural issues in scholarly publishing. Its reliance on subscription-based access reinforces the dominance of commercial publishers and does little to promote the principles of Open Access (OA).

In contrast, Diamond Open Access (Diamond OA) presents a transformative and equitable alternative. This model eliminates subscription fees and Article Processing Charges (APCs), democratizing access to knowledge and shifting control over scholarly publishing to academic communities. To align with the long-term goals outlined in India's Science, Technology, and Innovation Policy ([STIP](#)) 2020, India must view ONOS as a transitional measure while investing in building a robust, sustainable Open Access ecosystem centered on Diamond OA principles.

The ONOS Model: A Solution Fraught with Complexities

The ONOS initiative provides uniform access to academic resources across Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in India, addressing the immediate needs of researchers and students who previously faced unequal access to journals due to financial or institutional constraints. However, the subscription-based nature of ONOS brings with it several significant challenges that limit its long-term utility.

Reliance on Subscriptions

ONOS consolidates access to journals but remains fundamentally tied to recurring negotiations with commercial publishers. This dependence means that access to academic resources is neither guaranteed nor permanent. The financial burden of renewing these agreements falls on the government, and as journal subscription costs continue to rise, the sustainability of this model becomes increasingly uncertain.

Restricted Access and Global Disparities

While ONOS ensures access for Indian citizens, it does so in a siloed manner, limiting collaboration and knowledge sharing with researchers from other countries. This national focus contradicts the global ethos of Open Access, which advocates for unrestricted, worldwide sharing of knowledge. Furthermore, the subscription model perpetuates inequities in global scholarly communication, as many institutions outside the system remain excluded.

Reinforcement of Commercial Publishing Dominance

By negotiating with large, for-profit publishers, ONOS strengthens their oligopolistic control over academic publishing. This dominance marginalizes community-led publishing initiatives and stifles efforts to decentralize scholarly communication, which is a core principle of the OA movement. Instead of challenging the status quo, ONOS inadvertently entrenches it further.

Diamond Open Access: A Vision for Transformation

Unlike subscription-based models like ONOS, Diamond Open Access offers a sustainable, inclusive, and transformative alternative. It eliminates financial barriers for both readers and authors, ensuring that knowledge is freely accessible to everyone. The costs associated with Diamond OA are covered through public funding, institutional support, or academic consortia, allowing academic communities to reclaim control over the publishing process.

Key Advantages of Diamond OA

1. **Global Equity:** Diamond OA removes the financial barriers that limit access to research, ensuring that institutions and researchers in underfunded regions can participate in and contribute to global knowledge exchange.
2. **Community Ownership:** By empowering academic societies, universities, and research institutions to take control of publishing processes, Diamond OA decentralizes the system and reduces reliance on profit-driven entities.
3. **Sustainability:** Diamond OA aligns with India's STIP 2020, which advocates for Open Science, national repositories, and barrier-free access to publicly funded research. This alignment ensures long-term sustainability through public and institutional support.
4. **Democratization of Knowledge:** The Diamond OA model promotes multilingual and regional publishing, which is particularly relevant for a diverse country like India. This inclusivity ensures that research outputs are accessible in multiple languages, catering to a broader audience.

Lessons from Global Practices

India's approach to scholarly publishing can benefit from the successes and limitations of international initiatives such as Egypt's Knowledge Bank and Uruguay's hybrid model.

Egypt's Knowledge Bank

Egypt's [initiative](#) provides nationwide access to resources from major publishers, much like ONOS. However, it remains subscription-based, maintaining dependence on commercial publishers. While it addresses immediate access needs, it does not contribute to the long-term sustainability or independence of scholarly communication.

Uruguay's Hybrid Model

Uruguay combines centralized access with strong advocacy for Open Access through regional platforms like [Latindex](#), [SciELO](#), and [Redalyc](#). This balanced approach integrates the immediate benefits of subscription-based access with a long-term vision for Open Access, prioritizing community-driven publishing initiatives.

Uruguay's emphasis on regional collaboration and multilingual publishing provides a valuable roadmap for India. By adopting similar strategies, India can ensure that its scholarly communication ecosystem is both inclusive and sustainable.

Addressing the Challenges of ONOS

The ONOS initiative, poses risks to the broader Open Access movement. One key concern is that it may lead policymakers to deprioritize investments in community-led initiatives like Diamond OA. This could undermine the momentum of the OA movement, as subscription models might be perceived as sufficient solutions to access disparities.

Furthermore, ONOS reinforces the dependency on commercial publishers, contradicting the OA movement's goal of disrupting monopolistic practices. By funnelling resources into subscription deals, ONOS risks diverting attention and funding away from sustainable, community-driven publishing models. Finally, the national focus of ONOS limits its potential to foster global collaboration, a cornerstone of Open Access principles.

Building a Diamond Open Access Ecosystem in India

To establish Diamond Open Access as the foundation of India's scholarly publishing ecosystem, a multifaceted strategy is required. This strategy should include robust policy frameworks, significant investments in infrastructure, capacity-building initiatives, governance reforms, and advocacy efforts.

Policy Frameworks

India should adopt a National Open Access Policy mandating that all publicly funded research be published in Diamond OA journals or deposited in institutional repositories. Additionally, reforms in research evaluation systems, such as adopting the DORA Declaration, can encourage researchers to publish in OA venues by reducing the overemphasis on journal impact factors.

Infrastructure and Funding

Investments in infrastructure are critical for the success of Diamond OA. Platforms like [IndiaRxiv](#) and publishing platforms modelled on [AmeliCA](#) can serve as national hubs for preprints and Open Access journals. Public funding should support operational costs, including editorial workflows, peer review systems, and digital archiving. Leveraging existing tools like DSpace, ePrints, and Open Journal Systems (OJS) can ensure cost-effective and efficient repository management.

Capacity Building and Multilingual Publishing

Training programs for researchers, editors, and librarians can equip stakeholders with the skills necessary for OA publishing. Supporting regional and multilingual journals will enhance the accessibility and reach of Indian research, reflecting the country's linguistic and cultural diversity.

Governance and Community Ownership

Transparent governance structures are essential to oversee the management of Diamond OA initiatives. Collaborative networks of universities, libraries, and research institutions can share resources and expertise, ensuring accountability and quality standards in publishing.

Advocacy and Outreach

Advocacy efforts should communicate the benefits of Diamond OA to researchers, policymakers, and the public. Emphasizing the increased visibility, equity, and impact of OA can foster a cultural shift toward inclusive knowledge sharing. Here is the greater role of the Open Access India, a community of practice advocating for Open Access, Open Data and Open Education (Open Science) in India.

Existing Efforts to Advance Diamond Open Access in India

India is making significant strides in promoting Diamond Open Access (OA) through collaborative efforts by the [Open Access India](#) community, the Indian Council of Agricultural Research ([ICAR](#)), and the Council of Scientific & Industrial Research ([CSIR](#)). These initiatives leverage Open Journal Systems (OJS) to streamline and support not-for-profit publishing, ensuring that knowledge remains accessible to all without imposing financial barriers.

Open Access India Platform

The Open Access India community is at the forefront of this movement, actively developing a Diamond Open Access Journals platform hosted at [IndiaJOL](#). This platform facilitates the entire publication workflow, from manuscript submission to dissemination, without charging fees to authors or readers. By embodying the core principles of Diamond OA, the platform not only promotes equitable access to research but also amplifies the visibility of scholarly work, enabling it to reach a global audience.

ICAR's Platform for Agricultural Research

The Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR) has adopted OJS to manage its journals, providing a centralized [platform](#) for publications from State Agricultural Universities (SAUs) and societies within the National Agricultural Research System. This initiative ensures that critical agricultural research is accessible, well-organized, and disseminated effectively through a unified infrastructure.

CSIR's Streamlined Publication Process

The Council of Scientific & Industrial Research (CSIR) uses [OJS](#) to manage its suite of journals, ensuring a seamless and efficient publication process for its diverse research outputs. By adhering to Open Access principles, CSIR enhances the visibility and impact of its research while contributing to the broader goals of equitable knowledge sharing.

India's Leadership in the Global South

India is uniquely positioned to lead the Global South in advancing equitable scholarly communication. Initiatives like AmeliCA and Redalyc in Latin America provide valuable blueprints for community-driven Open Access. These platforms prioritize multilingual publishing, regional representation, and equity, addressing disparities faced by underrepresented regions.

By adopting and scaling these models, India can support regional and multilingual journals, build national repositories, and foster international collaborations. This approach aligns with India's STIP 2020 and establishes the country as a global leader in Open Science.

A Path Toward Equitable Knowledge Dissemination

India's ONOS initiative towards addressing immediate access disparities is a short-term fix that does not address the systemic issues in scholarly publishing. Diamond Open Access offers a transformative and sustainable path forward, ensuring that research outputs are accessible to everyone, everywhere.

By investing in Diamond OA, India can align its scholarly communication practices with the principles of equity, inclusivity, and sustainability. This vision positions India as a global leader in Open Science, demonstrating that knowledge can and should remain a public good, free from the constraints of profit-driven systems. Through strategic investments in policy, infrastructure, and advocacy, India can reshape the academic publishing landscape, ensuring that knowledge truly belongs to everyone.

Note: This blog post was created with the assistance of ChatGPT, an AI language model developed by OpenAI, to refine and organize the content

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